

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ASTROCYTES: BIOLOGY AND FUNCTION IN THE BRAIN

Doina Victor,

Student at "Nicolae Testemițanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy

Globa Tatiana

PhD, university lecturer

Department Histology Cytology and Embryology

"Nicolae Testemițanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy

Abstract

Astrocytes, also known as astroglia, are characteristic star-shaped glial cells in the brain and spinal cord. They are involved in the regulation of synaptic activity, plasticity, neurotransmitter homeostasis and extracellular ion balance, having a crucial role in neural network and cognitive functions. Alteration of astrocytic functionality resulting from the combination of loss of normal homeostasis-maintaining functions and acquisition of toxic functions, proved to be a key mechanism in a series of CNS neurodegenerative pathologies such as huntington's disease, alzheimer's, parkinson's, prion diseases, epilepsy, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, etc. Advances in transdifferentiation technology have opened up the possibility of directly inducing non-neuronal cells, such as astrocytes, to transform them into neuronal cells, both in vitro and in vivo.

Keywords: Neuroglia, astrocyte, blood brain barrier, GFAP, neurodegeneration.

Materials and methods: This article was written based on the scientific resources available on the platforms PubMed, Medscape, Science Direct, OxfordAcademic. From all the analyzed studies, only the articles that represent a major scientific interest and are based on a truthful bibliographic substrate were included in the bibliographic list on which the given research is based. Based on this volume of accumulated materials, the respective study was developed in compliance with the regulations in force and the correct exposure of the analyzed information.

Glial cells were first discovered in the 19th century by the French physician René Dutrochet, who described the presence of small globules in the nervous system of molluscs. However, the term "nervekitt" (nerve glue) was introduced only in 1856 by the German pathologist Rudolph Virchow to describe this type of connective tissue of the central nervous system. [2] Decades of research have demonstrated that these cells have a specific role in maintaining brain tissue homeostasis. In particular, astrocytes, so named for their star-like shape, are active players in the dynamic signaling of the central nervous system.[5]

Astrocytes represent the most numerous glial cells in the brain and are characterized by the intense expression of glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) that increases with age. Also, there are four structurally and anatomically distinct classes of GFAP+ astrocytes in the human brain: interlaminar, located in layers I and II; protoplasmic in layers III and IV; varicose projections in layers V and VI; and fibrous astrocytes in the white matter. [7]

Astroglia are involved in the regulation of synaptic activity, plasticity, neurotransmitter homeostasis, and extracellular ion balance, playing a crucial role in neural network and cognitive functions.[9] In the mammalian brain, astrocytic cells delineate the micro-architectonics by separating the gray matter into relatively

independent structural units. Astrocytes occupy their own territory and form micro-anatomical domains through their processes. In these anatomical areas, astrocyte membranes cover synapses, neuronal membranes, and send processes to surround the wall of nearby blood vessels. This complex of astrocytes, neurons, and blood vessels is known as the neurovascular unit. They also have a crucial role in the regulation of plasticity, neurotransmitter homeostasis and extracellular ion balance, having an essential role in the neural network and cognitive functions. [3]

Alteration of astrocytic functionality has been shown to be a key mechanism in a number of CNS pathologies. In the case of neurodegenerative diseases, the involvement of astrocytes is probably the result of the combination of the loss of normal homeostasis-maintaining functions and the acquisition of toxic functions. Reactive astrogliosis represents how astrocytes, the main supporting cells of the CNS, respond to tissue damage and is a gradual process that involves a series of cellular changes, from hypertrophy to proliferation and migration.[6] The extent and nature of the astrocyte response is influenced by the context in which CNS damage occurs, as well as its duration, nature. Reactive astrocytes have the ability to secrete a wide range of extracellular molecules, including inflammatory modulators, chemokines, cytokines and neurotrophic factors. These molecules can be either neuroprotective (such as interleukin-6 and transforming growth factor- β [TGF- β]) or neurotoxic (such as interleukin-1 β and tumor necrosis factor- α [TNF- α]). [1] Pathophysiologically, protein aggregates are found in astrocytes that disrupt normal functions, the results of which can lead to a series of CNS diseases such as Huntington's disease, Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, prion diseases, epilepsy, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, etc. [8]

In CNS lesions, there is a massive loss of neurons, and the endogenous resources are not able to satisfy tissue needs. New neurons created through neurogenesis account for less than 1% of the total loss. Advances in transdifferentiation technology have opened up the possibility of directly inducing non-neuronal cells, such as astrocytes, to transform them into neuronal cells, both in vitro and in vivo. Astrocytes are more closely related to neurons because they share primitive progenitor cells. Inhibition of astrocyte-

specific signaling and activation of neuronal signaling can promote direct transdifferentiation of astrocytes into neurons without going through the stem cell stage. Therefore, they are potential candidates to be transdifferentiated into functional neurons. Transdifferentiation of astrocytes into neurons may help replace neurons lost following ischemic stroke, while limiting the formation of glial scars that prevent axonal regeneration and recovery of nerve function.[10]

These encouraging discoveries in the field of cellular transdifferentiation with iPSCs (induced pluripotent stem cells) technologies represent a new perspective in the treatment of CNS diseases.[4]

References

- Hayatdavoudi P., Hosseini M., Hajali V., Hosseini A., Rajabian A. The role of astrocytes in epileptic disorders. In: *Physiological Reports*. 2022, nr. 10 (6), doi:10.14814/PHY2.15239
- Hubbard JA., Binder DK. Chapter 1 - History of Astrocytes.; 2016. Accessed February 17, 2023. <http://www.sciencedirect.com/5070/book/9780128024010/astrocytes-and-epilepsy>
- Matthew M. Boisvert. Astrocytes Across Time and Space.; 2018. Accessed November 26, 2022. https://escholarship.org/content/qt11s690rm/qt11s690rm_no-Splash_947c354ae1a6c28ce78d0828bd0636a0.pdf
- Mollinari C., Zhao J., Lupacchini L., Garaci E., Merlo D., Pei G. Transdifferentiation: a new promise for neurodegenerative diseases. In: *Cell Death & Disease* 2018 9:8. 2018, nr. 9 (8), pp. 1-9. doi:10.1038/s41419-018-0891-4
- Oberheim NA., Takano T., Han X., et al. Uniquely Hominid Features of Adult Human Astrocytes. In: *The Journal of Neuroscience*. 2009, nr. 29

(10), pp. 3276. doi:10.1523/JNEUROSCI.4707-08.2009

6. Phatnani H., Maniatis T. Astrocytes in Neurodegenerative Disease. In: *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Biology*. 2015, nr. 7 (6), pp. 1-18. doi:10.1101/CSHPERSPECT.A020628

7. Ribeiro PFM., Ventura-Antunes L., Gabi M., et al. The human cerebral cortex is neither one nor many: neuronal distribution reveals two quantitatively different zones in the gray matter, three in the white matter, and explains local variations in cortical folding. In: *Frontiers in neuroanatomy*. 2013, nr. 7 (SEP), doi:10.3389/FNANA.2013.00028

8. Siracusa R., Fusco R., Cuzzocrea S. Astrocytes: Role and functions in brain pathologies. In: *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2019, nr. 10 (SEP), pp. 1114. doi:10.3389/FPHAR.2019.01114/BIBTEX

9. Verkhatsky A., Ann N., Bush O., Nedergaard M., Butt A. The Special Case of Human Astrocytes. In: *Neuroglia* 2018, Vol 1, Pages 21-29. 2018, nr. 1 (1), pp. 21-29. doi:10.3390/NEUROGLIA1010004

10. Astrocyte reactive în formarea cicatricilor gliale și unde se formează. | Descărcați diagrama științifică. Accessed February 23, 2023. https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Reactive-astrocytes-in-the-formation-of-glial-scar-and-where-they-form_fig1_328237801